

ENZYMES IN SNAKE VENOM. PART IV.

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The critical inactivation temperature of the proteolytic enzymes in the venoms of cobra (*Naja naja*), banded krait (*B. Fasciatus*), *Echis carinata* and *Vipera russelli* has been determined and has been found to be 55°, 53°, 55° and 62° respectively. The critical inactivation temperature of trypsin mixed with heated cobra venom is 60°. It has therefore been suggested that the proteolytic enzyme in snake venom is identical with trypsin.

In a number of papers published by Ghosh and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 450, 627 ; 1937, 14, 604) it has been shown that the venoms of cobra (*Naja naja*), Daboa (*Vipera russelli*), banded krait (*B. Fasciatus*) and *Echis carinata* contain a proteolytic enzyme which resembles trypsin in almost all the properties investigated so far. One of the characteristic properties of enzymes is their critical inactivation temperature, a temperature at which an enzyme loses one half of its original activity when heated for one hour. Although this temperature varies somewhat with the protein content of an enzyme preparation yet it is of much help in establishing the identity of an enzyme. In this paper, the results which have so far been obtained on the determination of the critical inactivation temperature of the proteinase present in the venoms of cobra, banded krait, Russell's viper and *Echis carinata* along with some results on the effect of heated and ordinary venom on the activity of trypsin, is recorded. It will be noted from these results that the temperature of critical inactivation of the proteinase contained in the different venoms, is quite close to that of trypsin admixed with proteins of cobra venom.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Determination of the Critical Inactivation Temperature.

A series of solution of a venom were prepared at different temperatures by dissolving it in water heated to the desired temperature. The solutions were maintained for one hour at the respective temperatures at which they were prepared. They were then quickly cooled under a tap and a fixed quantity (2 c.c.) was withdrawn from each solution and allowed to act separately on 18 c.c. of a 1.9% solution of casein mixed with phosphate buffer at p_H 7.2 and maintained at a temperature of 36° in a thermostat. The extent of hydrolysis was determined by withdrawing at suitable intervals of time 5 c.c. of the solution and titrating it by Sørensen's method (Formol titration). The results are recorded in the following tables. The concentration of the substrate (casein) was throughout 1.7%.

TABLE I.

Russell's viper venom, 0.2% solution. Critical inactivation temp., 62°.

Venom heated for 1 hour at	0.02N-Alkali required		Diff. between I and II.
	after 2 hrs. digestion.		
	I.	II.	
36°	7.45 c.c.	5.65 c.c.	1.80 c.c.
50°	7.40	5.65	1.75
60°	6.75	5.65	1.10
62°	6.55	5.65	0.90
65°	6.05	5.65	0.40
70°	5.70	5.65	0.05

TABLE II.

Cobra venom, 0.4% solution. Critical inactivation temp., 53°.

Venom heated for 2 hours at	0.02N-Alkali required		Diff. between I and II.
	after 2 hrs. digestion.		
	I.	II.	
36°	7.30 c.c.	6.45 c.c.	0.85 c.c.
50°	6.90	6.45	0.45
55°	6.60	6.45	0.15
60°	6.50	6.45	0.05
56°	6.45	6.45	0.00

TABLE III.

Krait venom, 0.4% solution. Critical inactivation temp., 55°.

The venom heated for 1 hour at	0.02N-Alkali required		Diff. between I and II.
	after 2 hrs. digestion.		
	I.	II.	
36°	5.70 c.c.	5.40 c.c.	0.30 c.c.
50°	5.65	5.40	0.25
55°	5.55	5.40	0.15
60°	5.40	5.40	0.00
65°	5.40	5.40	0.00

TABLE IV.

Echis carinata venom, 0.1% soln. Critical inactivation temp., 55°.

The venom heated for 1 hour at	0.01N-Alkali required		Diff. between I and II.
	after 2 hrs. digestion.		
	I.	II.	
36°	6.80 c.c.	5.30 c.c.	1.50 c.c.
50°	6.40	5.30	1.10
55°	6.10	5.30	0.80
60°	5.60	5.30	0.30
65°	5.30	5.30	0.00

TABLE V.

Enzyme used — trypsin (E. Merck 0.02% soln.) Critical inactivation temp., 50°.

Enzyme heated for 1 hour at	0.01N alkali required		Diff. between I and II.
	after 2 hrs. digestion.		
	I.	II.	
30°	6.80 c.c.	5.45 c.c.	1.35 c.c.
45°	6.35	5.45	0.90
50°	6.15	5.45	0.70
55°	5.55	5.45	0.10

TABLE VI.

Enzyme preparation used — trypsin dissolved in 2% cobra venom solution previously heated to 70°. Substrate used, casein 1.7%. Critical inactivation temperature, 60°.

The enzyme heated for 1 hour at	0.01N-Alkali required		Diff. between I and II.
	after 2 hrs. digestion.		
	I	II	
30°	10.65 c.c.	5.85 c.c.	4.80 c.c.
36°	10.65	5.85	4.80
50°	10.30	5.85	4.45
55°	9.65	5.85	3.80
60°	8.20	5.85	2.35
65°	6.75	5.85	0.90

It will be noticed from the data recorded in the Tables I-VI, that critical inactivation temperatures of the proteinase in the venoms of cobra, krait, *Echis carinata* and Russell's viper are 53°, 55°, 55°, and 62° respectively, while that of trypsin (E. Merck) is about 50° and that of trypsin dissolved in previously heated Cobra venom solution is 60°. It may be mentioned here that Arrhenius ("Immuno-Chemistry," 1907, p. 90) found 65° to be the critical inactivation temperature of trypsin, considering the fact that the critical inactivation temperature of trypsin may vary from 50° to 60° or to a still higher value depending on the nature and extent of the inert proteins associated with it, it is perhaps permissible to assume that the proteinases in the venoms used are one and the same enzyme, trypsin, but show somewhat different critical inactivation temperatures owing to the different kinds and quantities of proteins with which they are associated in the different venoms.

Effect of Heated and Ordinary Venom on the Activity of Trypsin.

In a previous publication (Ghosh and De, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 637) it has been shown that the venoms (not heated) of cobra and Russell's viper inhibit the activity of trypsin (E. Merck) and this has been attributed to the presence of some inhibitor of trypsin in the two venoms used. The effect of heat on the destruction of this inhibitor has been investigated and the results obtained, so far, are recorded in this paper. Solutions containing known amounts of venom were prepared and heated for one hour at temperatures above 70° so that the proteinase present in them is destroyed. 2 C.c. of the heated venom solution were then added to different flasks containing the substrate and other requisite substance. The p_H of the reaction media was adjusted at the desired value and they were buffered with phosphate solution of the same p_H . The volume of the reaction media was 20 c.c. in each case. The concentrations of heated and ordinary venom were the same in all the flasks in which they were added. Similarly, the concentration of trypsin was kept the same in all the flasks in which it was added. The solutions were placed in a thermostat at 26° and the extent of hydrolysis was estimated by withdrawing 5 c.c. of the solution at suitable intervals of time and titrating it by Sørensen's method. The results are recorded in the following tables in which h.v. stands for heated venom, v for ordinary (*i.e.* not heated) venom, T for trypsin, h.v. + T for mixtures of heated venom and trypsin and v + T for mixtures of ordinary venom and trypsin. The control consists of the substrate solution only.

TABLE VII.

Cobra venom = 0.1 % soln. Substrate used = 1.7% gelatin (Difco) soln.

pH.	Period of digestion.	No. of c.c. of 0.01N-alkali required.					Control.	No.
		h.v.	v.	T.	h.v.+T.	v.+T.		
7.1	0 hrs.	4.80	4.80	4.85	4.80	4.85	4.80	1
	3	4.80	5.10	8.50	9.45	7.80	4.80	2
	Diff. bet. 1 & 2	0.00	0.30	3.65	4.95	2.95	0.00	
8.0	0	3.25	3.25	3.20	3.25	3.20	3.20	3
	3	3.25	3.65	6.95	7.90	6.50	3.20	4
	Diff. bet. 3 & 4	0.00	0.40	3.75	4.65	3.30	0.00	

Substrate used = 1.7 % casein solution.

7.1	0	4.45	4.45	4.45	4.45	4.45	4.40	5
	3	4.45	4.70	8.80	9.70	7.40	4.40	6
	Diff. bet. 5 & 6	0.00	0.25	4.35	5.25	2.95	0.00	
8.0	0	4.40	4.40	4.40	4.40	4.40	4.40	7
	3	4.40	4.70	8.45	10.15	7.14	4.40	8
	Diff. bet. 7 & 8	0.00	0.30	4.05	5.75	2.75	0.00	

TABLE VIII.

Banded krait venom = 0.1 % . Substrate used = 1.7 % gelatin (Difco) soln.

pH.	Period of digestion.	No. of c.c. of 0.01N-alkali required.					Control.	No.
		h.v.	v.	T.	h.v.+T.	v.+T.		
7.1	0 hrs	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	1
	3	4.00	4.10	7.35	8.20	8.25	4.00	2
	Diff. bet. 1 & 2	0.00	0.10	3.35	4.20	4.25	0.00	
8.0	0	2.20	3.20	3.20	3.20	3.20	3.15	3
	3	3.20	3.40	6.70	7.95	7.95	3.15	4
	Diff. bet. 5 & 4	0.00	0.20	3.50	4.75	4.75	0.00	

TABLE VIII (contd.).

p _h . Period of digestion.	No. of c.c. of 0.01			N-alkali required.		Control.	No.
	h.v.	v.	T.	h.v. + T.	v. + T.		
Substrate used = 1.7% casein solution.							
7.1	0 hrs.	4.80	4.80	4.80	4.80	4.75	5
	3 hrs.	4.80	4.90	9.70	10.20	10.20	4.75
Diff. bet. 5 & 6.		0.00	0.10	4.90	5.40	5.40	0.00
8.0	0 hrs.	4.40	4.40	4.40	4.40	4.40	7
	3 hrs.	4.40	4.60	9.00	10.05	9.50	4.40
Diff. bet. 7 & 8.		0.00	0.20	4.60	5.65	5.10	0.00

TABLE IX.

Russell's viper venom = 0.1% soln. Substrate = 1.7% casein soln.

p _h . Period of digestion.	No. of c.c. of 0.01			N alkali required.		Control.	No.
	h.v.,	v.	T.	h.v. + T.,	v. + T.,		
7.1	0 hrs.	4.95	4.95	4.95	4.95	4.95	1
	3 hrs.	4.95	5.35	8.80	6.80	7.20	4.90
Diff. bet. 1 & 2.		0.00	0.40	3.85	1.85	2.25	0.00
Substrate used = gelatin (Difco) solution (1.7%)							
7.1	0 hrs.	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	3
	3 hrs.	4.00	4.40	7.25	4.60	4.85	4.00
Diff. bet. 3 & 4		0.00	0.40	3.25	0.60	0.85	0.00

TABLE X.

Echis carinata venom = 0.1% solution.

Substrate = (Difco) gelatin 1.7% soln.

p _h . Period of digestion	No. of c.c.		of 0.02 T.	N-alkali required.		Control.	No.	
	h.v.	v.		h.v. + T.	v. + T.			
7.1	0 hrs.	4.00	4.05	4.05	4.00	4.05	1	
	3 hrs.	4.00	5.65	7.35	8.35	9.05	4.05	2
Diff. bet. 1 & 2.		0.00	1.60	3.30	4.35	5.00	0.00	
8.0	0 hrs.	3.35	3.40	3.35	3.35	3.40	3.35	3
	3 hrs.	3.35	5.25	6.85	7.75	8.50	3.35	4
Diff. bet. 3 & 4.		0.00	1.85	3.50	4.40	5.10	0.00	

TABLE X (Contd.).

P _n -	Period of digestion	No. of c.c. of 0.01. N-alkali required.		N-alkali required.		V. + T	Control.	No.
		h.v.	v.	T.	h.v. + T.			
Substrate used = 1.7% casein solution.								
7.1	0 hrs.	4.95	4.95	4.95	4.95	4.95	4.95	5
	3 hrs.	4.95	6.40	8.95	10.70	11.65	4.95	6
Diff. bet. 5 & 6.		0.00	1.45	4.00	5.75	6.70	0.00	
8.0	0 hrs.	4.35	4.35	4.35	4.35	4.35	4.35	7
	3 hrs.	4.35	5.60	8.15	10.00	10.85	4.35	8
Diff. bet. 7 & 8.		0.00	1.25	3.80	5.65	6.50	0.00	

It will be noticed from the data recorded above that the addition of solutions of venoms of cobra, banded krait and *echis carinata* previously heated at 70° for one hour to trypsin increases its activity markedly. The venoms of krait and *echis carinata*, even when they are not heated, activate trypsin but solutions of cobra venom which is not heated and Russell's viper venom whether heated or not, inhibit the activity of trypsin to an appreciable extent.

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